

THE ROLE OF APHORISMS

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A language shows the particular features of its literature, culture, traditions especially, aphorisms' role in reflecting of any language is considerable.

Aphorisms (from the Latin "aphorismsium" - aphorisms) can be well known, repeated and concrete saying with complete utterance as well as they express a truth, based on common sense or the practical experience of people. Several linguistics have given own definition to it.

Famous linguist W. Mieder gives a definition to a aphorism in his book: "A aphorisms is a short, generally known sentence of the folk which contains wisdom, truth, morals, and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed and memoizable form and which is handed down from generation to generation". It is obvious that aphorisms are usually based on metaphor and have figurative meaning. Mieder's definition is considered to be the best one among them. Because aphorisms are not a simple unit of a language, it is a ready-made sentence that gives metaphorical meaning with words of wisdom or traditional thoughts of people or nation.

We sometimes revive our desire for knowledge with the help of motivating phrases and inspiring sayings. Accordingly, in parallel with working on our mood, we will significantly increase our vocabulary and, on occasion, will be able to brag to our interlocutor about our knowledge of English catchphrases and idioms.

Throughout the history of mankind, the world has known many great thinkers and brilliant people. Some of them remained unknown to modern descendants, while others left famous works containing wise thoughts about life, love, education, relationships, etc. as a gift to the next generations. Subsequently, quotations from these works have

spread throughout the world, and have their own counterparts for each country. Today we will consider how these popular aphorisms sound in English.

Of course, we don't limit ourselves to classical quotations, because our contemporaries can also boast of interesting expressions. Also, many phrases come into use thanks to modern films and books. So, we are waiting for a lot of categories, so for everyone there will be their own motivating and inspiring phrases in English.

At all times, people have tried to comprehend themselves, society, the purpose of the existence of this world. But only an outstanding thinker can notice important things in a series of gray everyday life. In this section, we will present wise statements about the structure of the world, which were left behind by great philosophers, scientists, writers and other famous figures of various historical eras, as well as unknown authors.

- The will to win, the desire to succeed, the urge to reach your full potential... these are the keys that will unlock the door to personal excellence.

- Follow your heart.

- The mind is everything. What you think you become.

Everyone, probably, noticed the glamorous and fashionable phrases about love on the pages of popular social networks? Agree, they often smell of falsehood and insincerity. Feeling a real experience and expressing it in a short phrase is a rare success that not everyone accompanies. We have selected the most sincere and best love phrases in English with translation that can warm cold hearts and awaken the brightest feeling in them.

- We hate the ones we love because they can cause the deepest suffering.

- All we need is love.

- Keep love in your heart. A life without it is like a sunless garden when the flowers are dead.

- Never compare your love story with those in the movies, because they are written by scriptwriters. Yours is written by God.

Friendship is the most important phenomenon of life, so it is not surprising that many winged expressions with meaning are composed about it. Anything can be found in friendly relations: devotion, help, betrayal, hypocrisy, and much more. All this range of feelings can be expressed with the help of small stable expressions. Consider what aphorisms, idioms and short phrases the English language contains on the topic of friendship.

- The best mirror is an old friend.
- It is easier to forgive an enemy than a friend.
- Everyone seems normal until you get to know them.
- One can always be kind to people about whom one cares nothing.
- Be loyal to the one who is loyal to you.
- It is better to be in chains with friends, than to be in a garden with strangers.
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THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Mieder W. International Aphorism Scholarship. New York: Garland Publishing, 1993
2. Gotthardt H.H., Varga M.A. (eds.) Introduction to Paremiology: A Comprehensive Guide to Proverb Studies. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2014
4. Teliya V.N. Phraseology in the context of culture. Languages of Russian culture. Moscow, 1999